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Determination of Stability Constants of 5-Methyl-Salicylidene-*p*-Nitroaniline Complexes with Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Mg²⁺

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THE successive stability constants of the complexes of 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-nitroaniline with various bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum *pH* titration techniques as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The Corning Model 12, a precision research *pH* meter with a combined glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for measuring 'B' values (*pH* meter readings) of the solutions. [H⁺] and *pH* values there from of the experimental solution were obtained from these B values using a standard calibration curve of [H⁺] vs *pH*. The changes in 'B' can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 unit.

The ligand 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-nitroaniline was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 5-methyl-salicylaldehyde and *p*-nitroaniline in methanol. The product was repeatedly crystallised from methanol (m.p. 167°).² The medium of titration was 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxan-water mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. The free acid, the free acid plus the ligand and the mixture of metal ion containing acid plus the ligand were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide (1.04 M). Metal perchlorates were prepared from metal salts of A.R. grade, using perchloric acid of A.R. grade. All the solutions were standardised complexometrically³ by E.D.T.A. titrations. The experimental details and computational methods are the same as described in the earlier communication⁴. The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and *pL*. The titrations were performed in duplicate to test the reproducibility.

It may be stated here that the reagent does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by the *t_c* taken from time to time of a sample titration mixture.

Since only one proton (of the phenolic OH group) per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y', the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The formation curve was obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A values against *pH* (Fig. 1) and is wave like. It extends over a range of 0.135 < \bar{n}_A < 0.995. The value of *pK*₁² which corresponds to the association of

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-nitroaniline.

proton to phenoxide ion of the reagent was evaluated from the half-integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. This was further corroborated from the plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right]$ vs *pH*.

\bar{n} and *pL* values were calculated and \bar{n} values were plotted against corresponding *pL* values to get the formation curve of metal complex ion equilibria (Fig. 2) from which the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were evaluated; these correspond to *pL* value at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were further corroborated from the plots of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}} \right]$ vs *pL* and $\log \left[\frac{2 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n} - 1} \right]$ vs *pL* respectively.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stabilities of the bivalent metal chelates was found to be Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺

Mg²⁺ and is in agreement with the Maley and Mellor order⁵.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of 5-methyl-salicylidene-p-nitro-aniline.

TABLE I—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

Cations	$t=25^\circ$				
	H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
log K ₁	10.90	8.7	6.6	5.88	4.17
log K ₂	—	6.66	—	—	—

* For proton association (H⁺), K₁ correspond to the species LH, while for metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML₁ and ML₂ respectively.

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Studies on Th(IV) and Zr(IV) Complexes of Oxygen Donor Ligands-V. Oxozirconium(IV) Complexes of Pyridine N-Oxide and 2,6-Lutidine N-Oxide†

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RECENTLY a large number of coordination compounds of pyridine N-oxide and its ring substituted derivatives with a wide variety of metal salts have been synthesised and characterised¹⁻³. Comparatively very little is known about the compounds of oxozirconium(IV) with aromatic amine N-oxides⁴⁻⁸. In this communication we describe some hitherto unknown complexes of pyridine N-oxide (PyO) and 2,6-lutidine N-oxide (LNO) with oxozirconium(IV) salts.

Experimental

ZrO(NO₃)₂·5H₂O and ZrOCl₂·4H₂O were obtained from BDH. Anhydrous ZrOCl₂ was prepared as reported earlier⁹. Crystalline zirconyl perchlorate was prepared by established method¹⁰. Other zirconyl halides were prepared from chloride salt. Pyridine N-oxide was prepared by the method of Ochiai¹¹, while 2,6-lutidine N-oxide was obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company Inc., U.S.A. Crystalline adducts were isolated by one of the following methods :

(a) In a typical experiment ethanolic solution of Lewis acid was mixed with slight excess of ligand. The reaction mixture was concentrated on a water bath. The concentrated mass was cooled to which an excess amount of diethyl ether was added—an oily viscous layer was obtained. This viscous layer was separated and washed thoroughly with ether. The viscous mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of absolute ethanol and again an excess of diethyl ether was added and a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with small amount of ethanol and ether, dried in vacuo over anhydrous CaCl₂.

(b) A solution of Lewis acid in ethanol was treated with an excess of the Lewis base in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed ca. 3h and the excess solvent was removed by distillation. The

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